

Kinetics and Mechanism of the Oxidation of Methionine by Pyridinium Chlorochromate

VINITA SHARMA, PRADEEP K. SHARMA and KALYAN K. BANERJI*

Department of Chemistry, J. N. V. University, Jodhpur-342 005

Manuscript received 19 March 1996, accepted 17 July 1996

The oxidation of methionine by pyridinium chlorochromate (PCC) leads to the formation of the corresponding sulphoxide. The reaction is first order with respect to PCC. Michaelis-Menten type kinetics have been observed with respect to methionine. The reaction has been studied in 19 organic solvents and the solvent effect has been analysed using multiparametric equations. A suitable mechanism has been proposed.

A number of reports on the oxidation of several substrates by pyridinium chlorochromate (PCC) are available in the literature¹⁻³. However, the kinetics of oxidation of methionine (Met), a naturally occurring sulphur-containing amino acid by PCC, have not been investigated, though the kinetics of oxidation of sulphides by PCC⁴ have been reported. Met is known to behave differently towards many oxidants relative to other amino acids^{5,6}. The mechanistic aspects are discussed.

Results and Discussion

The reactions were found to be first order with respect to PCC. Individual kinetic runs were strictly first order in PCC. Further, the first order rate coefficients did not vary with the initial concentration of PCC. The order with respect to Met is less than one (Table 1). A plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{Met}]$ is linear with an intercept on the rate ordinate. Thus

Michaelis-Menten type kinetics are observed with respect to Met. This leads to the following overall mechanism (equations 1 and 2) and rate law (4).

$$\text{Rate} = k_2 K [\text{Met}] [\text{PCC}] / (1 + K [\text{Met}]) \quad (3)$$

The dependence on the concentration of Met was studied at different temperatures and the values of K and k_2 were calculated from the double-reciprocal plots. The thermodynamic parameters of the complex formation and the activation parameters of the decomposition of the complexes were calculated from the values of K and k_2 respectively, at different temperatures (Tables 2 and 3). The reaction was studied at different acidities by adding varying amounts of TsOH to the reaction mixtures. The reaction is catalysed by acid. The hydrogen-ion dependence has the form: $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b[\text{H}^+]$ (Table 1).

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE OXIDATION OF Met BY PCC AT 293 K

$10^3 [\text{PCC}]$ mol dm ⁻³	$[\text{Met}]$ mol dm ⁻³	$[\text{TsOH}]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ s ⁻¹
1.0	0.02	0.0	8.91
1.0	0.05	0.0	19.5
1.0	0.10	0.0	31.4
1.0	0.20	0.0	46.5
1.0	0.40	0.0	61.0
1.0	0.70	0.0	70.0
1.0	1.20	0.0	76.1
1.0	2.00	0.0	80.3
2.0	0.40	0.0	60.2
4.0	0.40	0.0	61.0
8.0	0.40	0.0	62.1
12.0	0.40	0.0	60.8
1.0	0.20	0.1	57.0
1.0	0.20	0.3	78.6
1.0	0.20	0.5	100
1.0	0.20	0.8	128
1.0	0.20	1.0	153
1.0	0.40	0.0	61.5 ^a

^aContained 0.001 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

TABLE 2—FORMATION CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR THE FORMATION OF Met-PCC COMPLEX

K (dm ³ mol ⁻¹)				ΔH	ΔS	ΔG
293 K	303 K	313 K	323 K	kJ mol ⁻¹	J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	kJ mol ⁻¹
5.66	4.87	3.90	3.04	-18.9 ± 1.1	-42 ± 3	-6.6 ± 0.8
± 0.14	± 0.15	± 0.08	± 0.09			

TABLE 3—RATE CONSTANTS AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR DECOMPOSITION OF Met-PCC COMPLEX

$10^3 k_2$ (s ⁻¹)				ΔH^*	ΔS^*	ΔG^*
293 K	303 K	313 K	323 K	kJ mol ⁻¹	J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	kJ mol ⁻¹
8.75	17.4	35.0	71.3	52.4 ± 1.0	-106 ± 3	83.9 ± 0.8
± 0.22	± 0.3	± 0.7	± 1.5			

The observed hydrogen-ion dependence suggests that the reaction follows two mechanistic pathways, one acid-independent, another acid-dependent. The acid-catalysis may well be attributed to a protonation of PCC (equation 4) to yield a stronger oxidant and electrophile, with both the protonated and unprotonated forms being reactive. The formation of a protonated species of PCC has also been reported earlier^{2,3},

Induced polymerization of acrylonitrile: The oxidation of Met by PCC, in an atmosphere of nitrogen, failed to induce the polymerization of acrylonitrile. Further, the addition of acrylonitrile had no effect on the rate (Table 1). Thus the operation of a one-electron oxidation, giving rise to free radicals, is unlikely in this reaction.

TABLE 4—FORMATION CONSTANTS AND RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE DECOMPOSITION OF Met-PCC COMPLEX IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS AT 303 K

Solvent	K $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$	10^4 $k_2 \text{s}^{-1}$
Chloroform	5.02	151
1,2-Dichloroethane	4.95	145
Dichloromethane	5.08	118
DMSO	4.30	323
Acetone	4.46	100
<i>N,N</i> -Dimethylformamide	4.87	174
Butanone	4.20	75.7
Nitrobenzene	4.92	14.8
Benzene	4.58	42.7
Cyclohexane	4.85	6.70
Toluene	5.00	29.5
Acetophenone	4.88	117
Tetrahydrofuran	4.61	50.0
<i>t</i> -Butyl alcohol	4.43	89.2
1,4-Dioxane	5.12	60.3
1,2-Dimethoxyethane	4.73	43.7
Ethyl acetate	4.95	63.1
Carbon disulphide	4.68	20.9
Acetic acid	4.35	140

Solvent effect: The oxidation of Met by PCC was studied in 19 organic solvents. The choice of solvent was limited by the solubility of PCC and its reaction with primary and secondary alcohols. There was no reaction with the solvent chosen. The kinetics were similar in all the solvents. The values of K and k_2 are recorded in Table 4. A perusal of the data shows that the formation constants do not vary much with the nature of the solvents. However, the rate constants, k_2 varied considerably with the solvents. The rate constants, k_2 , in eighteen solvents (CS_2 was not considered, as the complete range of solvent parameters was not available) were correlated in terms of the linear solvation energy relationship (equation 5) of Kamlet *et al.*⁷,

$$\log k_2 = A_0 + p\pi^* + b\beta + a\alpha \quad (5)$$

In this equation, π^* represents the solvent polarity, β the hydrogen bond acceptor basicities, α the hydrogen bond donor acidity and A_0 the intercept term. It may be mentioned here that out of the 18 solvents, 12 have a value of zero for α . The results of correlation analyses in terms of equation (5), a biparametric equation involving π^* and β , and separately with π^* and β are given below (equations 6–9),

$$\log k_2 = -2.96 + 1.04\pi^* + 0.16\beta + 0.49\alpha \quad (6)$$

(±0.05) (±0.29) (±0.27)

$$R^2 = 0.4881; \text{sd} = 0.32; n = 18; \psi = 0.60$$

$$\log k_2 = -2.84 + 0.87(\pm 0.36)\pi^* + 0.32(\pm 0.29)\beta \quad (7)$$

$$R^2 = 0.3694; \text{sd} = 0.34; n = 18; \psi = 0.66$$

$$\log k_2 = -2.78 + 0.96(\pm 0.35)\pi^* \quad (8)$$

$$r^2 = 0.3182; \text{sd} = 0.34; n = 18; \psi = 0.68$$

$$\log k_2 = -2.33 + 0.48(\pm 0.33)\beta \quad (9)$$

$$r^2 = 0.1184; \text{sd} = 0.39; n = 18; \psi = 0.83$$

where n is the number of data points and ψ is the Exner's statistical parameter⁸.

The triparametric equation⁷ explains only *ca.* 49% of the effect of solvent on the oxidation. Further, by Exner's criterion also the correlation is poor (*cf.* equation 6). The major contribution is of solvent polarity. It alone accounted for *ca.* 32% of the data. Both β and α play relatively minor roles.

The data on the solvent effect were analysed in terms of Swain's equation⁹ of cation- and anion-solvating concept of the solvents also (equation 10),

$$\log k_2 = aA + bB + C \quad (10)$$

where A represents the anion-solvating power of the solvent, B the cation-solvating power and C the intercept term. ($A + B$) is postulated to represent the solvent polarity. The rates in different solvents were analysed in terms of equation (10), separately with A and B and with ($A + B$),

$$\log k_2 = 1.19(\pm 0.04)A + 1.39(\pm 0.05)B - 3.28 \quad (11)$$

$$R^2 = 0.9890; \text{sd} = 0.04; n = 19; \psi = 0.08$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.08(\pm 0.25)A - 2.83 \quad (12)$$

$$r^2 = 0.3603; \text{sd} = 0.32; n = 19; \psi = 0.65$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.22(\pm 0.40)B - 3.47 \quad (13)$$

$$r^2 = 0.5272; \text{sd} = 0.27; n = 19; \psi = 0.54$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.26 \pm 0.04(A + B) - 3.29 \quad (14)$$

$$r^2 = 0.9819; \text{sd} = 0.05; n = 19; \psi = 0.10$$

The rates of oxidation of methionine in different solvents show an excellent correlation in Swain's equation (equation 11) with both the cation- and anion-solvating pow-

ers playing significant roles, though the contribution of the cation-solvation is slightly more than that of the anion-solvation. The solvent polarity, represented by $(A + B)$, also accounted for *ca.* 98% of the data. However, the correlations separately with A and B were poor. In view of the fact that solvent polarity is able to account for *ca.* 98% of the data, an attempt was made to correlate the rate with the relative permittivity of the solvent. However, a plot of $\log k_2$ against the inverse of the relative permittivity is not linear ($r^2 = 0.6060$; $sd = 0.25$; $\psi = 0.48$).

Mechanism : In view of the absence of any effect of radical scavenger, acrylonitrile, on the reaction rate, it is unlikely that a one-electron reaction giving rise to free radicals, is operative in this oxidation. The observed data can be explained on the basis of a mechanism involving a rate-determining electrophilic attack by PCC-oxygen on the methionine-sulphur (equation 15). Similar mechanism has been suggested for the oxidation of sulphides by PFC¹⁰, periodate ion¹¹ and hydrogen peroxide¹². The electrophilic

attack on the sulphide-sulphur can be viewed as an S_N2 reaction. An S_N2 -like transition state is supported by the observed solvent effect. The oxidation may involve a cyclic transition state as suggested in many reactions of chromium(VI)¹³. The cyclic transition state will be highly strained in view of the apical position of a lone-pair of electrons or an alkyl group (equation 16). The formation of cyclic transition state entails a more exacting specificity of orientation and should result in a much larger negative entropy of activation than that observed.

Experimental

PCC was prepared by the reported method¹ Methionine (Merck) was used as supplied. Solvents were purified by the usual methods Toluene-*p*-sulphonic acid (TsOH)

was used as a source of hydrogen ions.

The product analysis was carried out under kinetic conditions. The oxidation of Met resulted in the formation of the corresponding sulphoxide. The sulphoxide was determined by the reported method¹⁴. The yield of the sulphoxide was $91 \pm 3\%$. The oxidation state of chromium in the spent reaction mixture, determined by an iodometric method, was 4.02 ± 0.11 . The overall reaction may be written as equation (1).

where, $R = \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}(\text{NH}_2)\text{COOH}$.

Kinetic measurements : The reactions were followed under pseudo-first order conditions keeping a large excess ($\times 15$ or greater) of Met over PCC. Temperature was kept constant to $\pm 0.1\text{K}$. The solvent was *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF), unless specified otherwise. The reactions were followed by monitoring the decrease in the concentration of PCC spectrophotometrically at 356 nm for up to 80% of the reaction. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) were evaluated from the linear ($r = 0.990-0.999$) plots of $\log [\text{PCC}]$ against time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rate constants were reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to U.G.C. and C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial support.

References

1. E. J. COREY and W. J. SUGGS, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1975, 2647.
2. K. K. BANERJI, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1978, 639; *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 1978, 193; *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1978, 51, 2732; *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1979, 17, 300; *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1983, 22, 413, 650.
3. M. SETH, A. MATHUR and K. K. BANERJI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1990, 63, 3640.
4. G. P. PANIGRAHI and D. D. MAHAPATRO, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1981, 13, 85.
5. V. SHARMA, S. MITTAL and K. K. BANERJI, *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 1966, 264.
6. D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, S. ANANDA and N. M. M. GOWDA, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1985, 39.
7. M. J. KAMLET, J. L. M. ABBODD, M. H. ABRAHAM and R. W. TAFT, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1983, 48, 2877, and references cited therein.
8. O. EXNER, *Collect. Chem. Czech. Commun.*, 1966, 31, 3222.
9. C. G. SWAIN, M. S. SWAIN, A. L. POWELL and S. ALUMNI, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1983, 105, 502.
10. K. K. BANERJI, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1988, 2065.
11. F. RUFF and A. KUCSMAN, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1985, 683.
12. G. MODENA and L. MAIOLLI, *Gazz. Chim. Ital.*, 1957, 87, 1306.
13. Y. W. CHANG and F. H. WESTHEIMER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 82, 1401; J. ROCEK and F. H. WESTHEIMER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 84, 2241.
14. J. MITCHELL, "Organic Analysis", Interscience, New York, 1953, Vol. 1, p. 375.